

ISic0814

Architrave recording two duumvirs

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

sandstone

Object

architrave

Editor

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Attributed by Fiorentini 2009: 101 n.5 to the architrave of the portico of the gymnasium

Coordinates

37.293371, 13.586410

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

A large architrave block preserving mouldings with the guttae from the base of triglyphs along the top edge. Appears intact on all sides, but broken/damaged at the right-hand end. The rear and the left end are finished.

Dimensions

Height 45 cm

Width 176 cm

Depth 52 cm

Layout

A single line of deep cut very regular Greek letters with some traces of stucco preserved within the letters (and elsewhere on the stone)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 85-100 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: n/a mm

Text

1. ἐπὶ δυῶν ἀνδρῶν (vac.undefin) · (vac.undefin) Λ[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

In the dummvirate of L[---]

Commentary

The reference to duumviri

implies Roman administration of the city, which requires a date after 44 BC.

Wilson and Manganaro both take this to imply that the text must belong in the narrow window of the civil war period, 44-36 BC, under Sextus Pompeius, but this is largely predicated on the assumption that the use of Greek would be impossible subsequently in a city of municipal status, whereas the widespread existence of (Latin) municipia on the island from some time in the Augustan period is clear, and the occasional use/persistence of Greek into the Augustan period is also attested, so restriction to such a narrow window of time seems unnecessary. The example of the Greek inscription on the gymnasium benches (ISic1418 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1418>]), which appears to be clearly Augustan in date, and the further indication that this stone comes from the portico of the gymnasium

Digital identifiers:

TM 644906

EDR 136234

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1966.0168bis

Griffo, P. 1963. Contributi epigrafici agrigentini. *Kokalos*. 9: 163-184. At 178-179 no.8 tav.57 fig.9-10

De Waele, J. 1971. Acragas Graeca: die historische Topographie des griechischen Akragas auf Sizilien. 1, Historischer Teil. *Archeologische studiën van het Nederlands Instituut te Rome*. 's-Gravenhage. At 37-38

Moretti, L. 1976. Un ginnasio per Agrigento. *Rivista di Filologia e di Istruzione Classica*. 104: 182-186. At 184

Griffo, P. 1985. Ancora su due epigrafi agrigentine. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 59: 53-64. At 53

Griffo, P. 1987. Il museo archeologico regionale di Agrigento. Rome. At 190-192

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 360 n.89

Fiorentini, G. 1996. Il ginnasio di Agrigento. *Kokalos*. 42: 5-14. At 13

Fiorentini, G. 2009. Il ginnasio di Agrigento. *Sicilia Antiqua*. 6: 71-109. At 101 n.5

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0814. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339550>